

Synthesis of ZnO nanocomposites for photovoltaic applications

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Abstract : Nano structured zinc oxide (ZnO) have received considerable attention due to their distinguished performance in the electronic, optical and photonic devices. In this paper, we have prepared thin film of nanocomposites using different ratios of ZnO, TiO₂ and GO by simple mechanical stirring and ultra sonication. The single zinc oxide nanostructured particle was characterised by UV-Vis and its band gap energy was investigated. The prepared composite samples were further characterized using scanning electron microscope (SEM) to get the surface morphology. The current-voltage (I-V) characteristics of thin films of ZnO/TiO₂ and ZnO/TiO₂/GO nanocomposites were investigated. The FF (fill factor), I_{SC} (short circuit photocurrent), V_{OC} (open-circuit photo-voltage) and η (efficiency of the composite material for solar cell) were measured for all the nano-composites.

Keywords : ZnO, nanocomposites, band gap energy, I-V characteristics, TiO₂, GO.

Introduction

Composites of semiconducting oxides are extensively used as part of numerous electronic and optoelectronic devices like thin-film transistor (TFT), sensors and solar cells¹⁻⁷. A major limitation in all the thin film solar cell technologies is that their absorbance of near-bandgap light is ineffective, in particular for the indirect-band gap semiconductor silicon. Therefore, structuring the solar cell so that light is trapped inside, in order to increase the absorptance, is very important. Among metal oxides, zinc oxide (ZnO) is found to be most suitable and preferable, compared to other metal oxide since it is easily available semiconducting material and non-toxic.

Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) thin films have also the potential to greatly reduce the production costs of commercially produced silicon solar cells. To enhance the photo degradation efficiency of zinc oxide nanocomposites, coupled semiconductor nanocomposites of ZnO/TiO₂ have been prepared by several different processes, such solid-state reaction method^{8,11}, thermal evaporation^{9,10}, hydrothermal reaction^{12,13}, magnetron sputtering¹³, templating¹⁴, electro spinning¹⁵, deposition on other substrate^{16,17} and sol-gel process^{12,18-26} etc. Zinc oxide nanocomposites using titanium oxide and graphene oxide has been reported by hydrothermal method also. In order to

reduce the cost of photovoltaic's, fabrication costs also need to be decreased while maintaining high efficiencies.

In the present study, ZnO nanocomposites were prepared using TiO₂ and graphene oxide (GO) using a simple method of mechanical stirring and ultra sonication. We have synthesized ZnO nanoparticles via microwave irradiation method²⁷ and the synthesised ZnO nanoparticles were mixed with different ratios of TiO₂ and GO in order to get different types of nanocomposites for their suitable applications in solar cell. The current-voltage (I-V) characteristics of thin films of ZnO/TiO₂ and ZnO/TiO₂/GO nanocomposites were investigated. Short circuit photocurrent (J_{SC}), open-circuit photovoltage (V_{OC}), fill factor (FF) and efficiency of the solar cell (η) were measured for all the nanocomposites.

Experimental

Synthesis of materials :

Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles were prepared by our own method using microwave irradiation²⁷. Titanium oxide (TiO₂, 99%) and natural graphite powder (extra pure) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Graphene oxide (GO) was prepared from natural graphite using Hummers method²⁸. Double distilled water has been used during the experiments.

Preparation of ZnO/TiO₂ and ZnO/TiO₂/GO nanocomposites :

ZnO nanoparticles and TiO₂, taken in the ratio of 1 : 3 were mixed by mechanical stirring followed by ultra sonication of the mixture in distilled water. Similarly, ZnO, TiO₂ and GO were taken in 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 2 : 1 and 1 : 3 : 1 ratios and subjected to mechanical stirring followed by ultra sonication for few hours in distilled water. The solutions were then poured on glass slide and the slides were dried for 24 h at 100 °C . Thus thin films were obtained for further investigation in their electrical properties.

Photovoltaic characteristics :

The photovoltaic measurements of thin films of ZnO/TiO₂ and ZnO/TiO₂/GO nanocomposites were carried out using a PGSTAT 101 solar simulator with an irradiance of 100 mW cm⁻². The current-voltage characteristics of the cell were measured by applying external potential bias to the cell and measuring the generated photocurrent. The monochromator was incremented through the visible spectrum to generate the IPCE (incident photon to current conversion efficiency). Parameters such as FF, *I*_{SC}, *V*_{OC}, and η were measured for all the nanocomposites by two probes solar simulator.

Results

UV-Visible absorption spectroscopy is widely being used technique to examine the optical properties of nanosized particles and band gap is the major factor for determining the electrical conductivity. The absorption spectrum of ZnO nanoparticles was shown in Fig. 1. It exhibited a strong absorption band at about 364 nm shown in Fig. 1.

The I-V performance of the thin films of 1 : 3 ratio of ZnO/TiO₂ and 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 2 : 1, 1 : 3 : 1 ratios of ZnO/TiO₂/GO nanocomposites was determined. The measured UV-illuminated I-V characteristics were shown in Fig. 2(a, b, c and d) respectively. After investigation, it was observed that 1 : 3 ratio of ZnO/TiO₂ have FF of 0.043, *I*_{SC} value of 1.04, *V*_{OC} value of 0.353 V and efficiency of

Fig. 1. UV spectra of ZnO nanoparticles.

0.015% (Fig. 2a). After addition of GO with ZnO and TiO₂, the 1 : 1 : 1 composite film of ZnO/TiO₂/GO ratio was found to possess FF of 0.11, *I*_{SC} of 2.65, *V*_{OC} of 0.182 V and efficiency of 0.04% (Fig. 2b), whereas 1 : 2 : 1 have FF of 0.0832, *I*_{SC} value of 4.12, *V*_{OC} of 130, efficiency of 0.058% (Fig. 2c), where as 1 : 3 : 1 composite films have FF of 0.0587 and, *I*_{SC} values of 2.25, *V*_{OC} values of 0.258 and efficiencies of 0.094% (Fig. 2d).

The SEM image of ZnO nanoparticles is shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 4(a,b) showed the SEM images of 1 : 3 : 1 ratio of ZnO/TiO₂/GO nanocomposite. The SEM images was for the composites having better I-V performance, and after investigation interestingly it was observed that 1 : 3 : 1 ratio has better PCE compared to 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 : 1 ratios of ZnO/TiO₂/GO. The PCE was observed to be 0.015%.

Discussion

Nanocomposites of ZnO/TiO₂ and ZnO/TiO₂/GO were prepared on glass substrates using simple mechanical and thermal routes and dip coating method. The band gap energy of ZnO nanostructured was found to be approxi-

Fig. 2. (a,b,c,d) : I-V curves of 1 : 3 ratio of ZnO/TiO₂ and 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 2 : 1, 1 : 3 : 1 ratio of ZnO/TiO₂/GO nanocomposites.

Fig. 3. SEM image of ZnO nanoparticles.

mately around 3.41 eV as calculated from UV spectra. The I-V properties of thin films of the composites have

been investigated and it was found to be influenced by the ratios of the materials doped. The surface morphology of ZnO nanostructured and ZnO : TiO₂ : GO composites thin film were found to be porous and in the form of aggregates and also relevant to each other. Before formation of composites (Fig. 3), particles were found to be a bit distinct whereas after making into composites, the ZnO nanoparticles seen dispersed along with TiO₂ and GO. The I-V graph showed that the ratio of 1 : 3 : 1 of ZnO/TiO₂/GO have better efficiency. The values of V_{OC} were found rather small compared to other composites film^{2,8,9} and their efficiency also varies from 0.015% to 0.094%. Although the efficiencies were less compared to the reported but it can be used for future scope in solar applications.

Fig. 4. (a, b) : SEM images of thin films of ZnO/TiO₂/GO (1 : 3 : 1) nanocomposite.

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